

MODERN TRENDS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES**Teshaboyeva Nafisa Zubaydulla qizi**

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Annotation. Through this article, the author explores current trends of teaching and learning foreign languages in terms of teaching methods, approaches, evaluation, assignments, educational tools thanks to new developments in technology in our globalized era.

Key words: educational technology, innovation, creativity, critical thinking, motivating students, proficiency.

Аннотация. В этой статье автор исследует современные тенденции преподавания и изучения иностранных языков с точки зрения методов обучения, подходов, оценки, заданий, образовательных инструментов благодаря новым разработкам в области технологий в нашу глобализированную эпоху.

Ключевые слова: образовательные технологии, инновации, креативность, критическое мышление, мотивация студентов, владение языком.

Introduction

In today's fast-paced life in order to get a well-paid job, sincere colleagues, fast career progress it is of great significance to learn at least one foreign language. Coming today, English is considered to be "lingua franca" that means a language that is widely used in communication, conferences, education, policy, economy and others. Therefore, most people put high demand on mastering this language. Admittedly, each aspect of foreign language acquisition faced with up-to-date alterations because of technology integration. For example,

FL(Foreign Language) teaching methods.

Since educators began applying ed-tech (educational technology), this tool (Interactive whiteboards, projectors, tv, computers) has been easing teaching and learning processes successfully. Educational technology encompasses e-learning, instructional technology, information and communication technology (ICT) in education, learning technology, multimedia learning, technology-enhanced learning (TEL) and computer-based instruction (CBI). It is clear that, in the past it was common to see teacher-centred lessons in which mostly teachers move and speak without motivating pupils to be an integral part of the lesson. This, in turn, resulted in loss of enthusiasm, procrastinations, low proficiency level in learners of different levels. This way of teaching is called "grammar-translation" method. However, these days, in almost all educational institutions implementing learner-centred approach is highly prioritized by governing bodies, since quality education is rather essential than anything else. The term "learner-centred approach" is defined by encouraging learners to participate as actively as possible in the classroom.

How this can happen? By abandoning tedious lectures, the lessons become more engaging and productive whenever instructors organize discussions, debates, quizzes which make students use their problem-solving and critical thinking abilities. Therefore, gamification is considered to be one of the effective ways of keeping students' attention till the very end of the lesson as people in young ages have short attention span. Especially, in elementary schools it is necessary to teach through games, rewards, because elementary level learners have a difficulty to master a new language spontaneously.

Assigning and Evaluating.

Current education programs cover modern assessment ways and criteria so as to evaluate each student fairly. Besides that, assessment results bring more motivation to learn. Therefore, different ways of assessing students' knowledge are applied, including, collaborative assessments, peer evaluation, video interviewing, case studies, oral presentations, role-playing exercises, self-assessment and so on. For instance, **collaborative assessment** causes to the improvement of leadership skills, by this way students can learn how to work in groups, sharing knowledge and responsibilities. Next one is **peer evaluation**, evidently, students of all ages become able to assess each other with regards to their performance in a classroom by comparing and contrasting in a critical way. The other one is **Interviewing** is an effective and intriguing way of assessment through which learners can adopt and prepare for actual job interviews in the future. In addition, **oral assessments** have become widely used, since they gauge students' knowledge and skills based on the spoken word, typically guided by questions or small tasks. Oral assessments can take on different formats, including:

- presentation on a prepared topic (individual or group, live or recorded)
- simulations or demonstration of skills individually or with others (eg. client or patient)

There exist another common way of assessment, namely, **role-playing**, it is a technique that allows teachers to assess and analyze students' speaking skill development. This is accomplished through actions that will lead them to learn more vocabulary, have more grammar control, and become more fluent, less shy, more encouraged, and more capable of pronouncing words correctly.

Conclusion

Education technology can automate processes, improve information access, enable sharing of knowledge and data, duplicate information between media forms, curate important knowledge, visualize critical ideas and more. Moreover, learning technologies in the classroom are the tools, techniques, systems that facilitate, enable and promote learning. Furthermore they aid to boost skills, such as, creativity, decision making, innovation, critical thinking, information fluency and so on. These all mean that edtech plays a crucial role to achieve accelerating and prospering steps in education around the globe. Therefore, almost all teachers using up-to-date techniques of teaching, always, put preference on integrating technology into each part of the lesson, such as, explaining the new theme, revising the topic, assigning, evaluating, examinations and so on. By this way, they have an opportunity to obtain fast and fair results of students' performance after learning any new theme.

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